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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE OF COPYRIGHT COLLECTING SOCIETIES IN NIGERIA: ARE (SOME) INTERVENTIONS UNDER THE COPYRIGHT ACT LAWFUL?

By

Chijioke Okorie*

Abstract

As organisations that negotiate and grant licences for the use of copyright-protected materials and collect and distribute royalties to copyright owners, collecting societies are one of the important institutions of the copyright industry. Although good corporate governance is a *sine qua non* for the viability and efficiency of collecting societies, the competence of the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC) to act in the field of corporate governance of copyright collecting societies has been primarily based on the need to approve collecting societies to operate as such without a specific competence to intervene in that field. Recent intervention by NCC in the internal management of Copyright Society of Nigeria (COSON) is a test in ensuring corporate governance of collecting society or CMO in Nigeria. While collecting societies are within the regulatory competence of the NCC by virtue of the Copyright Act, they are also companies and the provisions of the Companies and Allied Matters Act 2004 stipulate steps that may be taken when a company's affairs are being run in a manner that is prejudicial to the company. This article discusses two critical issues relating to the application of corporate governance to CMO, namely; the legality of

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the NCC's actions in the corporate governance of collecting societies with reference to the suspension of COSON's operating licence; and secondly, whether there can be intervention under CAMA, in the corporate governance of collecting societies and, if so, what form such intervention may take. It concludes that while the NCC's actions in some corporate governance matters involving collecting societies under the Copyright Act may stand on shaky foundation, the NCC may proceed on firmer ground under the CAMA.

Introduction

Over the past few years, debate has ensued in Nigeria on how to address the issue of the corporate governance of collecting societies.¹ Although good corporate governance is a sine qua non for the viability and efficiency of any corporate entity, collecting societies inclusive, the events following the 2017 Annual General Meeting of one of Nigeria's collecting societies - the Collecting Society of Nigeria (COSON) - brought this matter to the fore.² In 2017, COSON had a meeting of the management board and removed its Chairman. There was a general meeting subsequently and the ousted chairman was reinstated. Several members of COSON were allegedly aggrieved with the way proceedings of that meeting and resolutions reached thereat were conducted. These members petitioned the statutory copyright sector regulator, the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC) reporting *inter alia*, the perceived irregularities in the conduct of the meeting.³ The

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1. The terms 'collecting society' and 'collective management organisation' are used in the literature and in different statutes to refer to the same entity. This paper prefers and uses the term, 'collecting society'.
 2. Chijioke I Okorie 'Corporate Governance of collecting Societies in Nigeria: Powers of the Copyright Sector Regulator.' (2018) 1 *IPLJ* 24.
 3. Afam Ezekude 'Text of press briefing by the Director General, Nigerian Copyright Commission, Mr Afam Ezekude, on the dispute in the Governing Board of Copyright Society of Nigeria Ltd/Gte (COSON)', (*Nigerian Copyright Commission*, 19 April 2018).
<<http://www.copyright.gov.ng/index.php/news-events/item/427-textof-press->

NCC issued a directive to COSON directing it to refrain from giving effect to the resolutions reached at the meeting and instead, convene another meeting at which new directors are to be elected as per COSON's articles of association. When COSON failed to comply with the directive, the NCC issued a notice pursuant to Regulation 19(2) of the Copyright (Collective Management Organisation) Regulations 2007 (CMO Regulations), suspending COSON's approval to operate.⁴ COSON has continued to operate asserting that as a company registered under the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA),⁵ the NCC had no powers to issue directives regarding its internal affairs (i.e. corporate governance).⁶ This raises the question of whether and to what extent the NCC have powers to intervene in the corporate governance of collecting societies and to suspend erring collecting societies on that basis.

This debate is not solely a Nigerian issue. Across the world, the issue of the corporate governance of collective societies and the regulation of the activities and management of collecting societies are at the forefront of the collective management discourse.⁷ In all, there is consensus that issues of

briefing-by-the-director-general-nigerian-copyright-commission-mr-afam-ezekudeon-the-dispute-in-the-governing-board-of-copyright-society-of-nigeria-ltd-gte-coson>accessed on 18 June 2018. Bob Aroture, 'Nigeria News|Press Briefing by Copyright Commission on Dispute in Governing Board of COSON' (*Nigerian Law Intellectual Property Watch Inc*, 1 May 2018)<<https://nlipw.com/nigeria-news-press-briefing-by-copyright-commission-on-dispute-in-governing-board-of-coson/>>accessed 29 July 2019.

4. Since that time, COSON's operating licence has expired. See 'COSON License Has Expired, Apply Now, Stakeholders Tell Okoroji – Starconnect Media' (*Starconnectmedia.com*, 2019) <<https://starconnectmedia.com/coson-license-has-expired-apply-now-stakeholders-tell-okoroji/>> accessed 29 July 2019.
5. Cap C20 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.
6. Bob Aroture (n 3).
7. Daniel Gervais 'Collective Management of Copyright and Related Rights.' Daniel (ed) (*Kluwer Law International BV* 2015); Lucie Guibault and S

corporate governance affect the very existence of the collecting societies themselves and incidences of poor corporate governance can lead to the ‘death’ of the affected collecting society,⁸ and for that reason, the corporate governance of collecting societies should be subject to some sort of regulation.

Possible solutions to address the corporate governance of collecting societies have been discussed in many jurisdictions. For instance, in the United Kingdom (UK), the collecting societies regulations require collecting societies to have a code of practice and empowers the relevant minister of state to impose such a code when a collecting society fails to establish one for itself.⁹ The UK regulation contains criteria in terms of provisions that the code should contain. Non-compliance with the Regulations and the code of practice (including failure to establish a code of practice) can attract sanctions.¹⁰ In Australia, the relevant copyright agency maintains regulatory

Schroff ‘Extended Collective Licensing for the Use of Out-of-Commerce Works in Europe: A Matter of Legitimacy *vis-à-vis* Rights Holders.’ (2018) 49(8) *IIC International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law* 1-2; Morten Hviid, Simone Schroff and John Street, ‘Regulating Collective Management Organizations by Competition: An Incomplete Answer to the Licensing Problem.’ (2016) 7 *J Intell Prop Info Tech & Elec Com L* 256.

8. See I Farlam and others (Copyright Review Commission) ‘Copyright Review Commission Report 2011’, <<https://www.gov.za/documents/copyright-review-commissionreport-2011>> accessed on 3 March 2018 46; See the decision of the South Gauteng High Court in Johannesburg in *Shapiro v South African Recording Rights Association Limited* judgment delivered on 6 November 2009.
9. See section 3 of the (UK) Copyright (Regulation of Relevant Licensing Bodies) Regulations 2014.
10. *Ibid.* See for example, PRS for Music ‘PRS for Music Code of Conduct’, available at <<https://www.prsformusic.com/-/media/files/prs-for-music/corporate/governance/code-of-conduct/prs-formusic-code-of-conduct.pdf>> (viewed 20 August 2018), British Copyright Council ‘Principles for Collective Management Organisations’ Codes of Conduct’, <http://www.britishcopyright.org/files/2614/1312/8143/BCCPGP_Policy_Framework_250512.pdf> accessed 20 August 2018.

oversight of collecting societies' corporate governance issues through a Code of Conduct adopted by or applicable to collecting societies.¹¹ This is meant to ensure accountability and transparency, and promote efficiency in the management of collecting societies. In South Africa, the Companies Act has specific provisions targeted at collecting societies and the King III Report on corporate governance has been applied to collecting societies.¹² There are also corporate governance-related provisions in South Africa's Collecting Societies Regulations 2006.

In the case of Nigeria, the focus has been on the CMO Regulations, which make several mandatory corporate governance-related provisions.¹³ The Copyright Act, which is the principal legislation, does not contain any specific reference to NCC's legislative and/or regulatory competence in the field of corporate governance of collecting societies per se. The competence of the NCC to act in the realm of the corporate governance of collecting societies has so far been primarily based on the need to give effect to the provisions of Section 39(7) of the Copyright Act empowering it to approve qualifying companies as collecting societies.¹⁴ This interpretation is based in part on the argument that the establishment and continued existence of collecting societies necessitates the institution of corporate governance structures, particularly those that enable appropriate conduct in the

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11. Australian Competition and Consumer Commission 'Code of Conduct for Collecting Societies' <<https://www.accc.gov.au/system/files/public-registers/documents/D09171037.pdf>> accessed on 20 August 2018).
 12. Institute of Directors Southern Africa 'King Report on Governance for South Africa 2009', available at https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iodsa.co.za/resource/resmgr/king_iii/King_Report_on_Governance_fo.pdf accessed 20 August 2018; See Copyright Review Commission (n 8).
 13. Okorie (n 2) 29.
 14. See preamble to the CMO Regulations 2007.

operation of collecting societies. In other words, since there is no self-standing legislative and/or regulatory “corporate governance competence”, the NCC has usually relied on its general powers to approve qualifying collecting societies to operate as such. So far, this has resulted in a secondary (but mandatory) approach to corporate governance regulation, found in the CMO Regulations.

But, collecting societies are first and foremost, companies registered under the CAMA.¹⁵ Therefore, the secondary approach to corporate governance and the reliance on the notion of approval to operate as a basis to regulate corporate governance of collecting societies exist in a field where another statute – CAMA – also applies to collecting societies as companies limited by guarantee. Under CAMA, persons outside the company itself may only interfere in the internal affairs of the company in specified circumstances.¹⁶ Outside those circumstances, only the company has the powers to manage its internal affairs and may ratify its actions, where irregularly undertaken.¹⁷ Given the foregoing, the question arises whether the corporate governance provisions of the CMO Regulations were validly issued and whether the NCC may validly issue any kind of directive to collecting societies (such as the one leading to COSON’s licence suspension).

This article discusses: firstly, the compatibility with its powers under the Copyright Act of the NCC’s actions in the corporate governance of collecting societies, in particular actions such as the directives issued to COSON; and secondly, whether there can be intervention under CAMA, in the corporate governance of collecting societies and, if so, what

15. See s 39 of the Copyright Act.

16. See ss 299 and 300 of the CAMA.

17. *Ibid.* See also, Dorothy Nelson, ‘The Dilemma of the Shareholders under the Nigerian Company Law.’ (2015) 37 *JL Pol’y & Globalization* 89.

form such intervention may take. These questions are discussed *seriatim*. This article does not discuss the merits of the NCC intervening in the corporate governance of collecting societies as such, but solely its legal competence.¹⁸

After providing a brief overview of the provisions of the CMO Regulations that address the corporate governance of collecting societies, Section 2 of this article focuses on the first ambit of the compatibility question: it looks to the Copyright Act to explore the reach of the provisions that empowers the NCC to act in the realm of corporate governance including its issuance of the CMO Regulations. Section 3 examines the second ambit of the compatibility question and will consider the compatibility of the directives issued to COSON as earlier mentioned with the powers of the NCC. In other words, section 3 assesses the compatibility of the sources of NCC's legislative competence with a specific exercise of the competence – notably, the directives issued to COSON following its management and general meetings. The reach of the powers entrusted to the NCC under the Copyright Act suggests that some of NCC's actions in the corporate governance of collecting societies may stand on shaky doctrinal footing. In answering this question, this article sheds light on the extent of the NCC's legislative competence in the realm of corporate governance of collecting societies.¹⁹ It discusses certain factors that influence the exercise of the NCC's legislative competence, and that therefore shape the NCC's regulatory space in corporate governance matters.

18. For a discussion on the effectiveness of the NCC's powers in the corporate governance of collecting societies under the CMO Regulations, see Okorie 2018 (n2) 24. See also, IA Olubiyi and KI Adam 'An examination of the adequacy of the regulation of collecting societies in Nigeria.' (2017) 5 *IPLJ* 93. Chijioke I Okorie 'Corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria: Powers of the Copyright Sector Regulator.' (2018) 1 *IPLJ* 24.

19. *Ibid.*

Section 4 will consider the possibility of regulatory intervention under CAMA. In particular, it suggests that to this end the NCC and/or aggrieved members of any collecting society may rely on CAMA to bring erring collecting societies to order when the matter concerns the internal affairs of a collecting society. It considers the provisions of sections 300 to 304 of CAMA and argues that those CAMA provisions offer a (stronger) doctrinal hook on which the NCC may place its intervention in corporate governance matters and entrench good corporate governance practices in collecting societies.²⁰ Section 5 concludes.

Legislative Competence of the NCC in Corporate Governance *vis-à-vis* the CMO Regulations

As stated earlier, the CMO Regulations operate a mandatory system requiring collecting societies to comply in order to validly operate as such. To be issued a licence to operate as a collecting society, the provisions of the CMO Regulations stipulate that a collecting society must have a general assembly of all its members as well as a governing board responsible for taking decisions on behalf of such collecting society.²¹ The Regulations also stipulate the requirement for directors, chairman of the governing board and Chief Executive Officer of any collecting society and the level of knowledge they must be adjudged to have.²² Further, the Regulations require aspiring collecting societies to submit an undertaking from at least 5 (five) Directors including the chairman of the collecting society undertaking that the collecting society shall comply with provisions of the Copyright Act and the Regulations in respect

20. R J Smith 'Minority Shareholders and Corporate Irregularities.' (1978) 41 *Mod L Rev* 147.

21. See Regulation 2(3)(ii) and (iv) of the CMO Regulations. See also, ss 35 and 244(1) of the CAMA.

22. Regulation 2(3)(iii) of the CMO Regulations.

of the operations of the collecting society.²³ These are corporate governance provisions as they relate to structure and governance of the collecting society.²⁴

Apart from these corporate governance-related requirements needed for collecting societies to apply for a licence to operate, the discretion of the NCC in granting or refusing operating licences also means that collecting societies that do not have appropriate corporate governance structures may be refused licence. Furthermore, even after approval and issuance of licence to operate, the CMO Regulations stipulate other corporate governance requirements for collecting societies. For instance, each collecting society is required to prepare and submit a general report of its activities and an annual audited financial report in respect of its operations for the preceding year to the NCC not later than 1 July of each year.²⁵ The Regulations also require the directors of any collecting society to act ethically and to keep the accounts and operations of the society devoid of fraud and unethical conduct.²⁶ Where a director has been indicted for an offence in relation to the result of an audit of the account of the collecting society, the CMO Regulations require that the collecting society suspend such director.²⁷ These provisions are significant when viewed within the context of licence durations. Operating licences are not issued in perpetuity; they last for 3 years and then the relevant collecting society must apply for renewal in order to continue to validly operate.²⁸ It is argued that this limit on the approval period is another technique, which allow the NCC some room to “judge”

23. Regulation 2(2)(vi).

24. Some authors consider these provisions excessive. See Olubiyi and Adam (n 19).

25. Regulation 8(2) of the CMO Regulations.

26. Regulation 10(2).

27. Regulation 10(4).

28. Regulation 2(9).

collecting societies' conduct in the licence period, and only renew licences of collecting societies which have conducted themselves appropriately (i.e. collecting societies with sound corporate governance). The same argument applies to the powers of the NCC to revoke the licence of a collecting society that no longer meets the conditions for the grant of licence (i.e. collecting societies who fail to uphold good corporate governance structures).

Also, the CMO Regulations contain an omnibus or catchall provision, which requires each collecting society to comply with any directive issued by the NCC in respect of the collecting society or face sanctions ranging from a written caution, licence suspension and revocation. By virtue of Regulation 20, the NCC may direct a collecting society to take any step or action. Where the collecting society fails to act as directed or fails to act within the time stipulated, its licence may be suspended and subsequently revoked. Under this Regulation, the NCC may issue a corporate governance-related directive, which the relevant collecting society is expected to comply with. Furthermore, Regulation 2(2)(vi) which requires undertakings from Directors of collecting societies to comply with the Regulations in its operations, further cements the NCC's use of the Regulations to issue corporate governance directives. Omnibus provisions requiring collecting societies to comply with directives issued by the NCC may therefore procure good corporate governance practices from collecting societies.

Are these corporate-governance related provisions of the Regulations compatible with the powers of the NCC? The CMO Regulations being a subsidiary legislation must conform to the totality of the primary statute – the Copyright Act - enabling or authorizing the NCC as regulatory authority to

act.²⁹The Copyright Act as the principal copyright legislation can thus be seen as a somewhat formal “constitution” for the NCC, forming the basis for its lawmaking.³⁰The Copyright Act will also provide the benchmark for reviewing the actions of the NCC as a public body.³¹ Section 39(7) of the Copyright Act provides that the NCC, “shall have power to make regulations specifying the conditions to give effect to the purposes of” section 39 of the Act. Section 39(7) of the Copyright Act specifically mentions the type of measures that the NCC is allowed to take – regulations– which are subsidiary legislations.³² In terms of the conditions for the approval of collecting societies, the Copyright Act does give the NCC a wide discretion, as it is not prescriptive of the contents of the Regulations in so far as they relate to the conditions for approval of collecting societies.³³An examination of Section 39 of the Copyright Act in its entirety shows that its purposes relate to the approval of collecting societies to operate as such.³⁴ Section 39(2)(a) to (c) makes mandatory provisions as

29. See Jemina Benson ‘Delegated Legislation in Nigeria: The Challenges of Control.’ (2015) 17 *Eur JL Reform* 403; George Nwangwu ‘The legal framework for public-private partnerships (PPPs) in Nigeria: Untangling the complex web’ (2012) 7 *Eur Procurement & Pub. Private Partnership L Rev.* 268.

30. Peter Oluyede *Nigerian Administrative Law* (University Press 1995) 333.

31. See *Amasike v Reg- Gen CAC* (2010) 13 NWLR (Pt 1211) 337 at 399, paras B- D Also *Psychiatric Hospital Management Board v Ejitagha* (2000) 11 NWLR (Pt 677) 154.

32. *Ibid.*

33. *PMRS v NCC*, unreported Suit No. FHC/L/CS/61/2007 (4 June 2009); and *COSON v MCSN & Ors* unreported Suit No.: FHC/L/CS/1259/2017 (13 February 2018). For a critic of this provision, vis-à-vis CAMA, see OS Opadere ‘Complexities of Copyright Collective Management in Nigeria vis-à-vis the Desire for Economic Development’ in E Azinge and H Chuma-Okoro (eds) *Intellectual Property and Development: Perspectives of African Countries* (2013) 287-316.

34. This is surmised from the literal rule of statutory interpretation. The section under consideration, specifically permits regulations for the purpose of setting approval conditions for collecting societies. See Obinna B Okere ‘Judicial

conditions precedent to the grant of approval to operate as collecting societies. These conditions precedent require an aspiring collecting society to be a company limited by guarantee comprising of a substantial number of copyright owners as members and having the object, *inter alia* of negotiation and granting of licences, collection and distribution of royalties. These provisions are mandatory provisions in the Copyright Act that require the NCC to only grant approval to companies that are established under the CAMA. These provisions are also reiterated in the CMO Regulations.³⁵

Accordingly, the NCC has, through the CMO Regulations, used the requirements for approval to operate as a technique to regulate the corporate governance of collecting societies. In the CMO Regulations, section 39(2)(d) of the Copyright Act was invoked together with the establishment of rules necessary to give effect to the purpose of section 39 in its entirety. The provisions of the CMO Regulations in the field of corporate governance may therefore be justified under the need to set requirements for the approval of companies to act as collecting societies.³⁶

Given that the power to make regulations for the approval requirements of collecting societies is guaranteed under the Copyright Act, it may be tempting to quickly conclude that the NCC has the powers to issue any sort of directive to collecting societies. It may also be tempting to conclude that insofar as the CMO Regulations did not create categories of directives that

activism or passivity in interpreting the Nigerian constitution' (1987) 36(4) *International & Comparative Law Quarterly* 788-816.

35. See Regulation 2(2).

36. See preamble to the CMO Regulations which provides "Pursuant to the powers conferred on it under Section 39(7) of the Copyright Act Chapter C28, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, the Nigerian Copyright Commission hereby makes the following Regulations..." See also, *Aig-Imoukhuede v Ubah* (2015) 8 NWLR (Pt. 1462) 399 at page 453, paras *G-H (CA)*; *Osawe v Registrar, Trade Unions* (1985) 1 NWLR (Pt 4) 755 at 769.

may be issued by the NCC, every collecting society is obliged to accept all NCC's directives as validly issued and comply with all such directives once issued. It is submitted that such conclusions should not be hastily made. This is because the validity of any NCC directive depends on the nature of such directive. As argued in the next section, using the directive issued to COSON as a case study, the NCC's regulatory and legislative powers over collecting societies are not absolute. Instead, its powers are hinged on the Copyright Act as the principal and enabling legislation and particularly on the "approval to operate" competence. It may issue directives; but such directive must be tied to its powers to approve collecting societies to operate as such and/or its powers under the Copyright Act.³⁷

Are all Corporate Governance Directives issued by the NCC Lawful?

As stated in the introductory part of this article, the NCC issued a corporate governance-related directive to COSON. Specifically, COSON was asked to retain the directors appointed at its meeting until it held another meeting to conduct a "valid" election. The directives issued by the NCC in the case of COSON were directives: "not to give effect to resolutions taken at the Extraordinary General Meeting held on 19th December, 2017, except the resolution on distribution of royalties to members, which was within the legitimate process of the meeting; to convene its annual General meeting (AGM) within 60 working days and elect Directors/Governing Board in line with the provisions of its articles of association; taking into account the relevant articles in respect of qualification of directors; to appoint a competent Professional who shall henceforth be the Company Secretary/Secretary of the

37. Craies on Statute Law (5th ed) 310; Benson (n 30) 403.

Governing Board”. The chain of events that led to this directive originated from a complaint from some of COSON’s members alleging breach of sound corporate governance practices especially those required by COSON’s articles of association. In this instance, the directives issued by the NCC to COSON followed the NCC’s review of proceedings at the meeting of COSON’s Governing Board and members. Clearly, the matter was a dispute between members and concerned the issue of who would be appointed as directors and who is to validly make such appointment. In issuing the directives to COSON, the NCC took the view that by virtue of Regulation 2(2)(vi) of the CMO Regulations, COSON had an obligation to comply with “any directive issued by the Commission in line with its statutory powers” and non-compliance “may render the operations of a CMO subject to possible sanctions under the CMO Regulations”.³⁸ Essentially, the NCC took the view that it could validly issue directives related to such corporate governance matters pursuant to its powers under the Copyright Act as exercised through the CMO Regulations.

The corporate governance of collecting societies involves several areas – copyright, business structure, trade and competition, culture, and also internal management. Thus, it could be argued that the competence of the NCC to act in the field of corporate governance would require a broad interpretation of the legislative powers of the NCC. Should that be the case, an additional question would be how to interpret a legislative competence such as an approval to operate competence, which is stated in general terms, to include a corporate governance competence, which is an ancillary aspect of the approval to operate competence. Essentially, does the Copyright Act’s provision empowering the NCC to issue the CMO Regulations apply or extend to permit the NCC to issue

38. See Ezekude (n 3).

any manner of directives to collecting societies as it sees fit? This section conducts an analysis of the competence of the NCC to issue a directive pertaining to certain aspects of the corporate governance of a collecting society (including COSON). The need for this analysis is rooted in the nature of the NCC's legislative powers in the field of corporate governance, which are not unlimited and self-standing, and should therefore not be readily assumed. Basically, every NCC directive must have a competence basis – a norm that empowers the NCC to issue a directive on that subject matter.

The NCC is a public body and there is ample case law in Nigeria and in many jurisdictions regarding how a public body should exercise its powers. A consistent thread that runs through the bulk of case law on the exercise of discretionary powers by public bodies is that the exercise of discretion can be subject to challenge or review, and a public body is bound to act within the boundaries of its statutory powers, in good faith and reasonably in discharging its responsibilities.³⁹ The exercise of power can be subjected to judicial review to ensure that due process was followed and that the public body did not act ultra vires its powers.⁴⁰ While the courts will generally presume that an administrative act has been undertaken reasonably and honestly, the courts would not shut out evidence to the contrary.⁴¹ Thus, where the decision of a public body is challenged on the grounds that its decision was ultra vires or outside its statutory powers, for instance, the courts will not hesitate to entertain such actions and subject the decision of such public body to scrutiny.

39. See Oluyede (n 30) Oyelowo Oyewo *Modern Administrative Law and Practice in Nigeria*. (University of Lagos and Bookshop Limited, 2016).

40. See *Governor of Oyo v Folayan* (1995) NSCNJ 50; *The Attorney General of Lagos State v Eko Hotels Limited and Oha Limited* S C 147/2002.

41. See *Savannah Bank of Nigeria Plc v Central Bank of Nigeria and 2 others* [2009] All FWLR 939 at 975-978, paras E - F *Ibid*, 977, paras F-G

In conducting a judicial review of the decision made by a public body, courts may also be invited to consider whether such public body has acted with improper motives or exercised its discretionary powers in bad faith or to accomplish some purposes not intended by its grant.⁴² It follows, therefore, that where an enabling legislation stipulates the boundaries of discretionary powers, the courts will generally treat this as a prerequisite to the valid exercise of the power conferred. Where the subject matter of the decision or action falls outside the jurisdictional limit of the decision-maker, such will confer on the courts jurisdiction to conduct a judicial review of such decision which may result in its declaring the decision of the public body to be null and void.⁴³ By extension, the NCC has no absolute powers and its decisions are subject to judicial review and where they are made ultra vires the NCC's statutory powers or made outside the considerations discussed above, may be set aside.

As stated earlier, the consideration of the scope of the powers of the NCC must be undertaken from the Copyright Act. To examine the competence of the directives issued to COSON, it is important to consider the potential sources of competence – that is, provisions in the Copyright Act that can serve as a legal basis for the NCC to issue directives related to a corporate governance matter. As earlier stated, the Copyright Act does not give specific corporate governance legislative competence to the NCC. Three types of norms are relevant here, due to their applicability to collecting societies lawmaking: provisions empowering the NCC to establish the requirements for the grant of approval to operate, provisions establishing the objectives of the Copyright Act and provisions indicating the functions of the NCC. In the absence of a

42. See *R v District Officer for Kutia ex parte Atem* [1961] All NLR 51.

43. See *Savannah Bank of Nigeria Plc v Central Bank of Nigeria and 2 others supra*.

specific corporate governance competence, other norms of the Copyright Act such as the objectives of the Act and the general functions of the NCC under the Copyright Act may influence collecting societies legislation in the field of corporate governance, namely by providing it with the normative content mostly absent from norms based on approval to operate.⁴⁴

While Section 39(7) of the Copyright Act stipulates that the NCC should make regulations regarding collecting societies, and which regulations may arguably extend to the field of corporate governance, it has little normative content in that regard. Rather, it is a functional competence, where the enabling legislation (the Copyright Act) grants the NCC powers to achieve an objective (the approval of collecting societies), but leave the choices as to the substantive content to the NCC's discretion.⁴⁵ This would make the corporate governance program greatly dependent on that discretion – in what concerns, e.g., the choice of the specific subjects of corporate governance to regulate and their respective regime. Taking the issue of structure as an example, the provisions of the CMO Regulations stipulating the requirement for directors, chairman of the governing board and Chief Executive Officer of the collecting society⁴⁶ and the level of knowledge they must be adjudged to have, may be justified because structural requirements may be deemed to be a significant requirement for approval to operate. Yet, section 39(7) Copyright Act gives no indication as to what substantive provisions are necessary to give effect to the purposes of section 39. In essence, the

44. Anne Winckel 'The Contextual Role of a Preamble in Statutory Interpretation.' (1999) 23 *Melb UL Rev* 184; Hakeem Olanakanmi Ijaiya *Judicial Approach to Interpretation of Constitution: A Study of Nigeria Australia, Canada and India* (Malthouse Press 2017) 66.

45. *Ibid*; See also Ana Ramalho *The Competence of the European Union in copyright lawmaking: A Normative Perspective of EU Powers for Copyright Harmonization* (Springer 2016) 18.

46. Regulation 1(2).

functional character of the powers given to the NCC under section 39(7) Copyright Act makes it a rather flexible competence norm, in the sense that it enables the NCC to delve into different aspects of corporate governance, so long as there is a link to the issue of giving effect to the purpose of section 39.

Section 39(7) will be a valid legal basis for the issuance of any directive including one that relates to corporate governance of collecting societies, first and foremost, where such directive falls within that involving the approval of collecting societies – i.e., where the NCC is stipulating conditions for the grant of approval to operate as collecting society. As the courts have made clear in cases where the primary legal basis for legislative competence permits the exercise of competence in ancillary areas, such legislative measure can have an impact on other aspects or pursue other aims, provided that the main goal of the measure is in fact the furtherance of the primary legal basis.⁴⁷ In other words, the express inclusion of the primary legal basis is the exclusion of other matters not mentioned. For the NCC, this opens the door for it to issue any directive to a collecting society, in so far as the approval goal (approval of companies to operate as collecting societies) remains the core objective of the measure. In the case of the directive issued to COSON, which relates to the internal management of COSON, the “ship has sailed” as far as the approval goal is concerned. Where the goal is to ensure accountability and transparency in COSON as a licensed collecting society, an audit may be an action that proceeds on a stronger doctrinal footing.

Even though other parts of section 39 such as subsection (2) makes mention of corporate governance matters such as membership of collecting societies (requiring that all members must be copyright owners) and objects of collecting societies

47. See *Attorney-General of the Federation & 2 Ors v Alhaji Atiku Abubakar & 3 Ors* (S C 31/2007) [2007] NGSC 118.

(requiring that they must have negotiation and granting of copyright licences and collection and distribution of royalties as their main objects), the creation of a framework for corporate governance and the nature of any directive issued by the NCC would need to be linked to the context of the rules necessary to give effect to the purposes of section 39. Section 39(2)(c) cannot be used as a self-standing competence to create just any kind of corporate governance rule – there must be a genuine link between the aim and content of the measure and the purpose of granting approval to collecting societies. Any directive issued by the NCC would need to be aimed at approval of collecting societies to operate as such.⁴⁸ Permitting any kind of directive including those outside the aim of approval of collecting societies would give the NCC unfettered regulatory control over the affairs of collecting societies. In such circumstances, a possible but extreme example would be the NCC issuing a directive requiring a collecting society to open a bank account with specified banks or open a particular type of bank account type.

Also, the long title to the Copyright Act may suggest an appropriate interpretation of the meaning of the expression, “matters relating to copyright”. In construing the provisions of an enactment, internal aids such as the long title and the preamble to the enactment, can be resorted to as an aid to the construction of the enactment, to arrive at the meaning of the words used in the enactment.⁴⁹ The long title and preamble to the Copyright Act states that the purpose of the Act is to “make provisions for the definition, protection, transfer, infringement of and remedy and penalty thereof of copyright in literary works, musical works, artistic works, cinematograph films,

48. See *Pharma-Deko Plc v FDC Ltd* (2015) 10 NWLR (Pt 1467) 225 at page 249, paras A – B (CA); *Orubu v NEC* (1988) 12 SC (Pt 3) 1; *Eguamwense v Amaghizemwen* (1993) 9 NWLR (Pt 315) 1.

49. *Ijaiya* (n 45) 66; See also *Ibid Aig-Imoukhuede v Ubah*.

sound recording, broadcast and other ancillary matters”. There is a presumption against implicit alteration of the law. The presumption is that the legislature does not intend to make any substantial alteration in the law beyond what it explicitly declares, either in express terms or by clear implication, or in other words, beyond the immediate scope and object of the statute. Accordingly, the courts would solve the problem of the scope of secondary powers by resorting to the objectives of the conferring legislation or provisions.⁵⁰ This means that the NCC will have stronger competence to act in the field of corporate governance where its actions are aligned to the objectives of the Copyright Act. It is argued that the NCC’s responsibility for matters affecting copyright relate to “definition, protection, transfer, infringement of and remedy and penalty thereof of copyright” and it can only act within its powers and to achieve those objectives. The duties assigned to the NCC thus provide the meaning and scope of NCC’s competences. The duties interpreted in line with the objectives of the Copyright Act itself are therefore a component of the NCC’s competence and serve to legitimize and validate its actions to the extent that they can often serve as an interpretative tool of competence norms.⁵¹ The stated objectives are especially relevant for the corporate governance of collecting societies, as they either touch upon copyright owners (i.e. protection, transfer and infringement of copyright) or the provision of access to copyright users in Nigeria.

The powers of the NCC are not limited to section 39 of the

50. See *SPDCN Ltd v Anaro* (2015) 12 NWLR (Pt 1472) 122 at page 171, paras A-F (SC); *E A Ind Ltd v NERFUND* (2009) 8 NWLR (Pt 1144) 535 at 573-574, paras E-C (CA); Maxwell on the Interpretation of Statutes (10th Ed), page 81; Craies on Statute Law (5th ed) p. 310.

51. See A A Oba ‘Statutes as their own interpretation: Internal aids to interpretation of statutes in Nigeria.’ (2004) 1(5) *UDUS Law Journal*; See also, *Attorney-General Lagos State v Attorney General of the Federation & Ors* (2003) 6 SCNJ 1.

Copyright Act. The Act grants competences or powers to the NCC to enable it to pursue certain objectives for which it was created.⁵²Section 34(3) provides for the role and duties of the NCC. Section 34(3)(a) states that the NCC has responsibility for all matters affecting copyright as provided under the Copyright Act. In other words, the NCC is exclusively competent to propose measures affecting copyright in Nigeria. In a way, this gives the concept a broad scope, since it appears to suffice that a particular aspect of corporate governance has relevance to copyright. However, it is not entirely clear whether directives relating to corporate governance matters such as meetings and appointment of directors should fall within “matters affecting copyright in Nigeria”. It is possible to argue that since collecting societies deal with both copyright owners and copyright users, their operations (including meetings and appointments) fall within matters affecting copyright in Nigeria. Directives concerning their meetings and the conduct of those who govern/manage their affairs may therefore involve the promotion of copyright. In this regard, the argument would be that the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies may be undertaken and related directives issued on the grounds that such falls within “matters affecting copyright in Nigeria”. Corollary to such argument, directives issued by the NCC under section 34(3)(a) with respect to the corporate governance of collecting societies would have specific link to copyright. But, such argument fails to take cognizance of the fact that the field of corporate governance involves different aspects and as such, not every corporate governance issue is connected to copyright. Rather, some corporate governance matters may at best have a tenuous link to copyright.

According to the Court of Appeal in *Williams v Edu*,⁵³ the question of internal management of a company is entirely a

52. See s 34 of the Copyright Act.

53. (2002) 3 NWLR (Pt 754) 400 at pages 411-412, paras H-C

matter for the company to address. Internal management involves *inter alia*, the question of whether the meeting ought or not to be held in a particular way; whether the directors ought or ought not to have sanctioned certain proceedings, which they are about to sanction and whether one director ought or ought not to be removed, and whether another director ought or ought not to have been appointed. It also involves the question of if there is one managing the affairs of the company who ought not to manage them, and if they are being managed in a way, which they ought not to be managed.⁵⁴ These questions are also relevant to the directives issued by the NCC as already listed above. Accordingly, it is argued that such questions weaken the competence of the NCC's directive, as it seems more squarely a matter for the company (collecting society) to address. Relying on the argument that the directive touches on corporate governance issues that will impact on the efficiency, accountability and transparency of collecting societies approved under section 39, and therefore the directive falls under "matters affecting copyright in Nigeria" is at best tenuous and at worst, ultra vires. In essence, it may be difficult to uphold the validity of the directive given the fact that it directly touches on the legal personality and powers of collecting societies as companies.

Hence, the main problem in this realm is that some corporate governance issues such as meetings and appointments of directors are issues which the provisions of CAMA; permit companies to address by itself.⁵⁵ In this regard, the provisions of section 299 of the CAMA are instructive. By virtue of section 299 of the CAMA, "where an irregularity has been committed in the course of a company's affairs or any wrong has been done to the company, only the company can

54. *Ibid*; See also *Tanimola and Others v Surveys and Mapping Geodata Ltd and Others* (1995) 6 NWLR (Pt 403) 617.

55. See *SPDCN Ltd v Anaro* (n 50).

sue to remedy that wrong and only the company can ratify the irregular conduct”. Based on this rule, even the courts will not interfere with the internal management of companies acting within their powers. Indeed, permitting persons outside the company itself to interfere with the internal management of a company may be futile as the company may ratify what has been done.⁵⁶As companies limited by guarantee, collecting societies may validly have other objects outside those mandated by the Copyright Act, i.e. negotiating and granting licenses, collecting and distributing royalties. Collecting societies therefore have the exclusive powers (subject to mandatory obligations under the CAMA) to make and change provisions in their articles of association for the governance of the company.⁵⁷ Therefore, even though there is pre-emption of collecting societies’ actions where the NCC decides to exercise its competence in the field of corporate governance, collecting societies have the freedom to manage their affairs and to choose who should manage their affairs. This significance of incorporation could thus be interpreted as delimiting the exercise of legislative competence of the NCC in corporate governance matters of collecting societies.⁵⁸ Companies (including collecting societies) enjoy an “internal management” leeway,⁵⁹ and the NCC has to assess whether a particular issue is within that internal management leeway.

In particular, the very nature of collecting societies as companies established under the CAMA may present a more viable alternative to the NCC in its regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies i.e. the way and manner a

56. D D Prentice, ‘Another Exception to the Rule in *Foss v Harbottle*.’ (1972) 35(3) *The Modern Law Review* 318-321.

57. ss 26 and 34 of CAMA.

58. See Agustin Spotorno ‘Why Is the Rule in *Foss v. Harbottle* Such an Important One?’ (2018)39(6) *Business Law Review*, 190–197.

59. *Ibid* Williams v Edu.

collecting society is controlled and directed so as to achieve its objectives.⁶⁰ This is because following the codification of the rule in the English case of *Foss v Harbottle*⁶¹ in section 299 of the CAMA, only a company (in this case, collecting societies) has the locus to complain of or rectify any wrong done to it or any irregularities in the conduct of its affairs.⁶² This means that even in cases where the matter pertains to the internal management of collecting societies, the requirement that the approval to operate be the underlying goal entails a causal relation between the legislative, regulatory or directional provisions and the approval to operate as a collecting society, since an action not founded on the purpose of section 39 regarding the requirements for approval to operate is not enough to justify recourse to section 39(7) of the Copyright Act. As a result, it must be actually and objectively apparent from the legislative measure that its aim is indeed the approval of a company to operate as a collecting society. The criterion established for regulation of corporate governance under Section 39(7) is therefore a genuine nexus between the aim (and also the content) of the legislative measure, on the one hand, and the establishment of requirements for approval to operate, on the other.

In the case of COSON, an examination of the contravened directive shows that the NCC found irregularities in the general meeting at which the ousted chairman was reinstated. The directive to maintain status quo followed from NCC's finding of irregularities. That being the case, it is submitted that the NCC's directive to not give effect to resolutions reached at a

60. *Ibid* SPDCN Ltd v Anaro.

61. (1843) 58 ER 189.

62. *Ibid* Williams v Edu 411-412, paras H-C See also, *Ivory Merchant Bank v Makham Co Ltd* (2002) 1 NWLR (Pt 747) 74 (CA); *Ladejobi v Odotola Holdings Ltd* (2002) 3 NWLR (Pt. 753) 121 (CA); *Haston (Nig.) Ltd v ACB Plc* (2002) 12 NWLR (Pt. 782) 623 (SC); *Ibid* Tanimola & Others v Surveys and Mapping Geodata Ltd &Ors .

management and/or members' meeting are issues affecting the internal affairs of a company and clearly impinges on matters which COSON as a company may ratify. Regulatory intervention in such issues may amount to unnecessary and undue interference and a licence suspension or revocation based on such interference may not survive the scrutiny of judicial review.⁶³ When juxtaposed with the clear powers under Section 39(7) to make regulations for the approval of collecting societies, the issuance of directives relating to matters that may be legitimately addressed by collecting societies themselves by virtue of CAMA, may lack doctrinal footing. Because the foundation for such directives may be tenuous, a suspension and/or revocation of licence based on such directive may be successfully challenged.⁶⁴

The provisions of Section 34(3)(f) also support the above-stated position. By virtue of that provision, the NCC would be responsible for such other matters as relate to copyright as the Minister may direct from time to time. This seems to suggest that for matters relating to copyright, the NCC may only act based on the direction of the Minister.

Can Intervention in the Corporate Governance of Collecting Societies be made under CAMA?

Section 39(2)(a) to (c) makes mandatory provisions as conditions precedent to the grant of approval to operate as collecting societies. These conditions precedent require an aspiring collecting society to be a company limited by guarantee comprising of a substantial number of copyright owners as members and having the object, *inter alia* of negotiation and granting of licences, collection and distribution

63. *Ibid Savannah Bank of Nigeria Plc v Central Bank of Nigeria and 2 others*

64. This is based on the principle of law as expressed in the Latin maxim is *ex nihilo nihil fit*, idest, out of nothing, nothing comes. See *Theodore Maiyaki Bala, Modern Practice of Civil Litigation in Nigeria* (Author House 2015); *Oloba v Akereja* (1988) 3 NWLR (Pt 84) 508 at 520.

of royalties. These provisions are mandatory provisions in the Copyright Act that require the NCC to only grant approval to companies that are established under the CAMA. By virtue of these provision, collecting societies fall within the ambit of CAMA.⁶⁵ It is worth considering how these CAMA provisions may provide stronger doctrinal footing in intervening in the internal affairs of collecting societies. As shown in the previous section, the doctrinal basis of the NCC's interference in certain internal affairs of collecting societies is quite shaky.

In terms of intervention where a collecting society purports to enter into an illegal or ultra vires transaction, contravenes its articles of association in the manner in which resolutions are made, cannot call a meeting to timeously address a wrong done to the company, Section 300 of the CAMA permits its members to apply to the court for an injunction or declaration. The import of the matters listed in Section 300 of CAMA relate to compliance with a company's memorandum and articles, agreed meeting procedures, appointment and removal of directors - the internal affairs of a company generally. As such, members through an application to court may address these matters.

Section 303 of the CAMA allows an applicant to bring an action in court in the name or on behalf of a company where the company's directors have acted wrongfully and will not take necessary action to protect the company despite being notified of the applicant's intention to seek redress in court and the action is in the best interest of the company. Such applicant may be a member of the company, a director or former director of the company, the Corporate Affairs Commission or any person, who in the opinion of the court is a proper person to make the application for relief.⁶⁶ It is argued that this last category of persons may include the NCC as the copyright

65. Ss 26 and 34 of CAMA.

66. S 309 of the CAMA.

sector regulator. These provisions suggest that licence suspension or revocation based on directives involving certain corporate governance-related matters of collecting societies may be made on stronger doctrinal footing where they proceed from an application to court under the CAMA. Where there is irregularity in the meetings and appointments of a collecting society in a manner prejudicial to the society or its members, the court may be called upon to pronounce them wrong or direct it to do the right thing. Moreover, the Court might establish some principles, guidelines or concepts that can then be used by the NCC in positive regulatory measures.

Moreover, these provisions should prompt the NCC to “partner” with collecting societies to formulate a code of corporate governance to guide the management and administration of collecting societies as registered companies. The requirement of adopting such code of corporate governance may also be made a condition precedent to the grant of approval to operate (and/or grant of licence renewal application) similar to the position in the UK and Australia. Such corporate governance code may for instance indicate tenure of chairman and directors of collecting societies. While the provisions of CAMA do not necessarily override the statutory powers of NCC to ensure transparency and accountability of collecting societies, they give the NCC a much stronger foundation to intervene in the internal affairs of collecting societies.

The NCC’s concern was that the proceedings at COSON’s meeting were marred with irregularities and contravened COSON’s articles of association which it undertook to the NCC to uphold, but the directive lacked a doctrinal hook on which to center its analysis of this connection. A reliance on CAMA would have allowed the NCC to achieve the same desired result, but on firmer doctrinal footing. Further, a court order is likely to have a higher compelling effect due to the

mandatory nature and zero compliance freedom they may leave to collecting societies.

Summary and Conclusions

The Copyright Act does not grant the NCC a specific competence to regulate the field of corporate governance. Even though the Act gives the NCC powers to stipulate terms and conditions for the grant of approval to operate as collecting societies, the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies must be linked to the NCC's responsibility for matters relating to copyright in Nigeria and the approval of collecting societies to operate. The problem of attaching the regulation of corporate governance to approval to operate needs, however, is that the concept of "approval to operate" does not give normative guidance regarding the substantial content of NCC action. In the absence of normative guidance, it is hard to assess the freedom left to collecting societies vis-à-vis the NCC intervention, as in principle it suffices that certain aspects of collective management needs to be regulated for purposes of approval to operate to trigger the application of legal bases for NCC action.

Nevertheless, the NCC intervention in the field of corporate governance has to consider not only a legal basis for action, but also certain factors that influence the use of its competence. These factors contribute to a clarification of the division of powers between the NCC and the collecting societies, and provide a better definition of how the NCC should proceed in its actions. As a result of these factors, the normative guidance absent from the main competence norms can be provided, and a few limits can also be imposed upon NCC action.

First, because companies (including collecting societies) are the first port of call in rectifying issues of corporate governance under CAMA, an internal management check must

be performed. The NCC has to justify the need for its intervention (for instance, through showing that the issue is not one that concerns events at meetings, appointment and removal of directors, but also by referring to relevant case law where applicable), and collecting societies are entitled to apply for judicial review to scrutinize the compliance of NCC's directives and regulations with the principles of legislative competence.

Second, the NCC must take the entirety of the Copyright Act into account in its actions in the field of corporate governance of collecting societies. There are several implications to this premise. At the outset, it obliges the NCC to consider the normative guidance provided by other provisions of the Copyright Act to legislations based on approval to operate needs, namely through the integration of other relevant objectives of the Copyright Act. As a result of said integration, the NCC must stay within the confines of copyright protection, transfer, infringement and remedies. The need to take into account all the relevant interests in copyright legislation is furthermore reinforced by the objectives and duties of the NCC, which encompass *inter alia* the responsibility for all matters relating to copyright.

Moreover, the consideration of the NCC's duties, the obligation to integrate the different objectives and the principles underlying judicial review of administrative actions combined also to result in the need to respect the collecting societies autonomy, particularly in what concerns internal management. While the NCC competence in corporate governance matters is limited, the NCC is still obliged to take some corporate governance aspects into account in its actions as it performs its copyright obligations. Even though there is no "corporate governance competence" proper in the Copyright Act, it can be argued that a conceptualization of competence as suggested above does give some indication regarding the

regulatory space of the NCC in the field of corporate governance. The competence basis used to issue the directives to COSON regarding its meeting was the CMO Regulations which were made pursuant to section 39 (7) of the Copyright Act. It is necessary that this norm addresses a question bordering on copyright rather than a question bordering on the internal management of a company such as a collecting society. In sum, even though the NCC is in principle entitled to act in the field of corporate governance for the purpose of granting approval to operate, the content of its actions must follow certain guidelines. These guidelines in turn reduce the discretionary leeway of the NCC and contribute to a better definition of the boundaries of NCC intervention in the field of corporate governance.

Based on this analysis of the extent of the NCC's powers in the field of corporate governance of collecting societies, it was concluded that the directives upon which the NCC suspended COSON's licence were *ultra-vires* the legislative powers of the NCC. Despite the submission that the CMO Regulations and the corporate governance related provisions contained therein are valid, some directives issued by NCC to approved collecting societies such as COSON (prior to 2017) may not pass scrutiny due to the nature of such directives. Based on a consideration of the provisions of sections 299, 300, 304 and 309 of CAMA, it was suggested that the NCC may proceed on stronger footing if it applied to court for intervention based on those sections. The CAMA provisions considered also offer the NCC legislative backing to implement a formal corporate governance code for collecting societies.